

A cross sectional study to assess the growth patterns among children in selected community areas of district patiala, punjab

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Abstract:

Growth is an essential feature of life of a child that distinguishes him or her from an adult. The process of growth starts from the time of conception and continues until child grows into adult. School age is the active growing phase of childhood. Primary school age is a dynamic period of physical growth as well as of mental development of child. The physical growth of children is reflecting by different anthropometric measurements especially weight and height. The aim the study to assess the growth patterns among children of selected community areas of District, Patiala,Punjab. A non- experimental quantitative research approach was adopted for the study and cross-sectional design was used in present study. Non probability convenient sampling technique was used to select 50 subjects. The tools used for the study were socio- Demographic data sheet, WHO growth charts (Z-Score).Weight-For-age: As per weight for age graph plotting, more than half of subjects 80%(n=41) were normal, 14%(n=7) were underweight, 4%(n=2) were severely underweight and 1(0.6%) was having growth problem. Height-For-Age: As height for age graph plotting, most of subjects 76%(n=38) were normal, 12%(n=6) were stunted and 12%(n=6) were severely stunted. BMI-For-Age: As per weight for height, majority of subjects 80%(n=40) were normal, 16%(n=8) were wasted, 4%(n=2) were severely wasted, 16(6.4%) were having risk of overweight, 7(2.8%) were overweight and 2(0.8%) were obese. There is association between BMI for age and Dietary pattern, Residence. And there is no association between BMI-for-age and Age, Gender, Age of enrolment in school, Type of family, No of sibling, Mothers education, Fathers education and socio economic status. Thus study concluded that maximum children were normal for weight-for-age, height-for-age and, BMI-for-age. There is association between BMI for age and Dietary pattern, Residence. And there is no association between BMI-for-age and others socio-demographic variables of the study.